

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Float deployment and data delivery to community via ARGO servers

Milestone MS29

**Funded by
the European Union**

**UK Research
and Innovation**

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

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Milestone report

Work Package	WP10 Subpolar circulation, heat delivery and water mass export
Milestone no. & title	MS29 Float deployment and data delivery to community via ARGO servers
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Version	Final
Due date	30 June 2025
Delivery date	22 May 2025

Cover sheet: Photo by Ivan Klopoushenko.

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Table of contents

1. Means of verification of the achievement of the milestone.....	4
2. Work performed and main achievements	4
References	5
Open Science	5

1. Means of verification of the achievement of the milestone

Within the OCEAN ICE project, the deployment of six profiling floats Argo ARVOR perpendicularly to the Bransfield front area at the Strait has been implemented in March 2025.

2. Work performed and main achievements

Six ARGO floats were deployed during the passage of Research Vessel RV Noosfera to the station Vernadsky on 14 and 15 of March 2025 successfully and transmitted their first messages according to the settings. Due to the worsening weather conditions, the location of the last float was slightly changed to the east. The final locations are reported in the picture below.

Fig. 1: Deployment locations of ARGO floats at the Bransfield Strait.

The locations are also reported in the table below.

Table 1: Coordinates of the ARGO floats.

NKE Number (Float serial number)	Lat	Lon
AI2600-25UA001	63°36.696' S	062°08.494' W
AI2600-25UA002	63°36.660' S	061°54.814' W
AI2600-25UA003	63°30.463' S	061°33.311' W
AI2600-25UA004	63°32.828' S	061°00.931' W
AI2600-25UA005(*)	63°33.196' S	060°34.447' W
AI2600-25UA006	63°19.0' S	060°03.1' W

Unfortunately, after completing two cycles, the signal transmission from the float AI2600-25UA005 was lost, most likely due to an ice event or grounding. For the remaining five ARGO floats, a modified sampling strategy was experimentally applied: a 16-day mission interval incorporating daily profiling cycles of 26 hours. This configuration was intended to enhance the detection of internal tides. As of 21 April 2025, all floats have reverted to the original 10-day cycle settings, with approximately 280 cycles remaining. The ARGO float dataset includes core physical parameters such as temperature, pressure, and conductivity, which are being utilised for the analysis of stratification and internal wave signatures in the Bransfield Strait and the central continental West Antarctic Peninsula (cWAP). These observations aim to improve understanding of seasonal water mass exchanges between the Weddell Sea and the central WAP.

References

Wang, X.; Moffat, C.; Dinniman, M.; Klinck, J.; Sutherland, D.; Aguiar-González, B. Variability and Dynamics of Along-Shore Exchange on the West Antarctic Peninsula (WAP) Continental Shelf. *J. Geophys. Res.* 2022, 127, e2021JC017645

Moffat C., Meredith M. (2018). Shelf–ocean exchange and hydrography west of the Antarctic Peninsula: A review. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* 376 (2122), 20170164. doi: 10.1098/rsta.2017.0164

Open Science

Datasets

The floats dataset are quality-controlled and uploaded regularly with the help of Coriolis and Euro-Argo to the <https://dataselection.euro-argo.eu/> and <https://www.ocean-ops.org/board>

Fig. 2: Page of the float serial number AI2600-25UA002 data transmitted to the Argo Fleet Monitoring <https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/float/4903872>